

8T and QFT – Analysis

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Abstract:

By analyzing each framework in terms of its axioms, mathematical disciplines and tools, its ideas behind the mechanisms that makes nature what it is, we can better grasp the similarities and differences between those two theories. One born in the early 20-century, the other revealed itself in early 21-century and already claimed its spot as a leading theory after predicting the fine structure constant from a Lorentz manifold.

Introduction

Quantum field theory has certain features that play a significant rule, and repeat themselves in one way or another along each epos of the theory. Among those, we can name the commutation and anti-commutation of bosons and fermions. The Dirac delta or interference known as a field, the operators of matter creating and destructing, cluster decomposition and Lorentz invariance. In addition to Feynman path integrations and diagrams. That being said, what are the mathematical axioms in which QFT is built upon? One would like to suggest those following axioms:

Axiom (1) – Nature is probabilistic

Axiom (2) – Fermions repeal, Bosons do not

Axiom (3) – There is only one set of rules

By the first axiom, we can include the Feynman diagrams and the Feynman path integrations. In addition to arbitrary amount of matters appear and disappear by operators we insert. By the second axiom the commutation and anti-commutation relation and the nature of spin and statistics. The third axiom, the Lorentz invariance and the entire set of symmetries and conservation laws, at quantum scale (Nother) and at large scale (Lorentz). Those three axioms also stand at the heart of 8-theory, so in essence the nature of those theories, their innate ideas about nature is the same. The difference is which ideas are describing the axioms and which objectives the theory is set to achieve. Quantum field theory searches for probability of certain occurrences, it does it amazingly well but lacks to provide the reason for those arbitrary numbers, such as coupling magnitudes. QFT uses integrations across the entire space-time that are impossible to solve. 8- Theory is also probabilistic in its nature, maybe even more than QFT. It has no data regarding any direction of motion, momenta, and location at any point and so on. Very little to no physical data is manifested in this theory. However, it does describe beautifully the magnitudes of the couplings, the reason each magnitude is what it is, the process of propagation and the dynamic nature of the forces.

The methods uses are partial differential equations, and the methods also uses in quantum field theory given by axiom (2), the commuting relation of fermions and bosons. It does not currently have complicated integrations over space-time or it can specify the decays as QFT. However, it does describe the dark energy in an accurate fashion given by its main equation, a varying Lorentz manifold. Gravity is within its domain of description as it was built upon the work of two of the greatest minds in science Einstein and Lorentz. It is also supported by the coupling constant equation and predict that graviton will be massless and that gravity is actually a combination of three net variations. The 8T has two arbitrary numbers less than QFT; it predicts infinite bosonic fields, which relate to Lorentz net curvature on the manifold. It also predicts infinite families below first generation, and thus does not face questions as to those arbitrary numbers.

8T and QFT both are described in terms of the Dirac delta. QFT uses the delta as a description for the wave equation, as a way to describe a complete set of states, alongside with a set of amplitudes. 8T uses the Dirac delta in more flexible manner, it applies to times that are different from zero as well, and describe how an arbitrary amount of curvature vanish into matter. Any net variation at a later continuation of time than describing a bosonic ripple field across the manifold, given by a variation of the Laplacian. While QFT is mainly physical, 8T is mainly and almost completely mathematical, the axioms at the heart of those theories are the same, the methods are similar, the 8T describe phenomena not within the realms of QFT, and QFT can calculate probabilities not within the realm of 8T. 8T is just as probabilistic as QFT, if not more. It validates Pauli Exclusion Principle and the fermionic and bosonic difference between spin and statistic, and have just one set of rules. This set of rules has three axioms:

Axiom (1): All universes are Lorentzian manifolds

Axiom (2): All Lorentzian manifolds are stationary

Axiom (3): Net Curvature on the manifold is a bosonic field. Net are Primes.

References

[1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)